

Interaction of Schiff Bases derived from Aromatic Aldehydes, Substituted Quinazoline-(3*H*)-4-ones with Chromium(III), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II)

M. KUMAR* and T. SHARMA

University Department of Chemistry, University of Bihar, Muzaffarpur-842 001

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Thirty one ionic, non-ionic, paramagnetic and diamagnetic complexes of stoichiometries $[ML_2X_2]X$, $[ML_2]X_2$, $[ML_2X_2]$, $[ML_2X_2]$, $[ML_2]X_2$ (where $M = Cr^{III}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} ; $L = MAQV$ or $PAQV$; $L' = PADE$) have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of their magnetic and spectral properties. Metal salts show more toxic effect on alga in comparison to their respective complexes and ligands.

THE coordination chemistry of Schiff bases as acyclic polydentate ligands having delocalised π -orbitals gained importance for over two decades because of their use as models of biological systems¹. In view of the interest involved in these compounds on account of their use in chemotherapy as well as wide range of stereochemistry in complexation with metal ions, three Schiff bases have now been synthesised, viz. pyridine-2-aldehyde-1,2-diaminoethane (PADE), 2-methyl-3-amino-4(3*H*)-quinazoline-vanillin (MAQV) and 2-phenyl-3-amino-4(3*H*)-quinazoline-vanillin (PAQV). The syntheses of Cr^{III} and several bivalent metal complexes are reported along with their characterisation by molar conductance, electronic, magnetic, nmr and esr spectral studies.

The biological activity of ligands and complexes have also been studied.

Experimental

Vanillin (Loba) and pyridine-2-aldehyde (Sigma) were used. Metal salts and solvents used were either of B.D.H. or Sarabhai make.

Pyridine-2-aldehyde-ethylenediamine: An equimolar mixture of pyridine-2-aldehyde and ethylenediamine was stirred and refluxed for 4 h. The mixture was then concentrated by evaporating the solvent to small volume and was kept in refrigerator overnight. A bright yellow precipitate was obtained after recrystallisation from ethanol and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$, m.p. 35° .

Ligand MAQV and PAQV: 2-Methyl-3-aminoquinazoline-4-one and 2-phenyl-3-aminoquinazoline-4-one were prepared as reported in the literature². MAQV and PAQV were prepared by mixing ethanolic solution of the respective 2-substituted-3-aminoquinazoline-4-one with ethanolic solution of vanillin in equimolar quantity. To the mixture a few drops of triethylamine (as catalyst) was then added and it was refluxed on a water-bath for about 10 h. On cooling, brown solids of MAQV and PAQV were obtained. The solids were washed, recrystallised from DMF and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$: MAQV, m.p. 120° ; PAQV, m.p. 160° .

Metal complexes with ligand PADE ($M = Cu^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} ; $X = Cl^-$, Br^- , I^- , ClO_4^- or NO_3^-): An ethanolic solution of the ligand was mixed with ethanolic/aqueous solution of the metal salt (1 : 1) with constant stirring and refluxed for 1–2 h. The resulting solid was washed with alcohol and ether, and dried under reduced pressure. M.p.s. of all the complexes were above 240° .

Metal complexes with MAQV and PAQV ($M = Cr^{III}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} ; $X = Cl^-$): The complexes of Cr^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were prepared by mixing the ethanolic solution of the metal chloride with the ethanolic solution of the

respective ligands (1 : 2) and refluxing for 8–10 h on a water-bath. pH was maintained at $\approx 7-8$ in all the cases by adding sodium acetate solution.

The complexes of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} were prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solution of the respective ligands with ethanolic solution of the metal chloride (1 : 1) for 8 h. pH of the solution was maintained at $\approx 7-8$ by the adding sodium acetate. All the complexes were recrystallised from methanol and were dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride. M.ps. of all the complexes were above 275° .

1H nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) were recorded using an EM 930 spectrometer and esr spectra were recorded at R.S.I.C., Madras. C, H and N analyses were carried out in Microanalytical Laboratory at I.I.T., Kanpur, and the metal and halides contents were estimated by standard methods³.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are partially soluble in common organic solvents but are appreciably soluble in DMF. The analytical data indicate their compositions as $CuLX_2$, CuL'_2X_2 ; $NiLX_2$, NiL'_2X_2 ; $CoLX_2$, CoL'_2X_2 ; $(CrL'_2Cl_2)Cl$; $ZnLX_2$, ZnL'_2X_2 ; $CdLCl_2$, CdL'_2Cl_2 and $HgLCl_2$, HgL'_2Cl_2 ; where $L=PADE$ and $L'=MAQV$ or $PAQV$. The molar conductance (in DMF at $1 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes were found in the range $110-120 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ indicating that they are 1 : 2 electrolytes⁴; whereas Cr^{III} complexes show molar conductance in the range $72-740 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ indicating that they are 1 : 1 electrolytes⁵. Molar conductance of all other complexes were found in the range $10-16 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ indicating their non-ionic nature⁴.

Infrared spectra: The ir spectra of all three ligands exhibit bands at $1630-1610 cm^{-1}$ ($C=N$)⁶. The ligand PADE shows additional band at $1540 cm^{-1}$ whereas MAQV and PAQV show band at $1690 cm^{-1}$ due to ring vibrations of the heterocyclic bases, i.e., $\nu_{pyridine}$ ⁷ and $\nu_{C=O}$ respectively. The downward shift of ν_{CH-N} , $\nu_{pyridine}$ (ring vibration) and $\nu_{C=O}$ bands by about 20, 30 and $45 cm^{-1}$ in the complexes formed by all the three ligands show coordination through amido oxygen⁸, azomethine nitrogen⁹ and pyridine nitrogen¹⁰. These have been further confirmed by the appearance of ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} bands at $480-545$ and $570-635 cm^{-1}$ respectively^{11,12}.

The band at $275-280 cm^{-1}$ in the complexes may be assigned to ν_{M-X} ($X=Cl$, Band I). As ν_{M-X} band did not split up, so halogen atoms are at *trans*-position. The ir spectra of the nitrate complexes show bands at ~ 1640 , ~ 1220 , ~ 1000 and $\sim 940 cm^{-1}$ whereas the perchlorate complexes show bands at ~ 1260 , ~ 1120 and $\sim 970 cm^{-1}$ suggesting the presence of coordinated nitrate¹³ and perchlorate¹⁴ anion.

Magnetic data and visible spectra: The Cu^{II} complexes with PADE show μ_{eff} values in the range $1.89-1.95 B.M.$ indicating their octahedral geometry. The small increase in the magnetic moment value of the Cu^{II} complexes can be ascribed to spin-orbit coupling¹⁵. The Cu^{II} complexes with MAQV and PAQV have magnetic moments in the range $2.16-2.18 B.M.$ Large orbital contribution to magnetic moment has been used as an evidence for tetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes^{16,17}. The Ni^{II} complexes possess μ_{eff} values in the range $2.85-3.26 B.M.$, which are suggestive of octahedral geometry. The magnetic moment values for the Co^{II} complexes show μ_{eff} in the range $3.96-4.03 B.M.$ which are much lower than the values expected for tetrahedral ($4.2-4.7 B.M.$) or octahedral ($4.7-5.2 B.M.$) cobalt(II) complexes. This lowering of magnetic moment values may be explained by assuming the coexistence of high-spin as well as low-spin states of Co^{II} ($t_{2g}^5 e_g^3 \rightleftharpoons t_{2g}^6 e_g^1$), the presence of antiferromagnetism or the polymeric nature of the complexes^{18,19}. The μ_{eff} values of the Co^{II} complexes with MAQV and PAQV ($4.92-5.00 B.M.$) agree well with the expected value for octahedral Co^{II} . The Cr^{III} complexes have magnetic moments value in good agreement with that reported for octahedral Cr^{III} complexes. The complexes of Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with PADE, MAQV and PAQV are diamagnetic and tetrahedral.

The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes with PADE exhibit a broad asymmetric ligand field band in the region $13400-13600 cm^{-1}$ ($\epsilon=1.0-11.3$) characteristic of distorted octahedral stereochemistry with D_{4h} symmetry²⁰. The Cu^{II} complexes with MAQV and PAQV exhibit two peaks around 8850 and $12360 cm^{-1}$. The crystal field theory of tetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes predicts only one transition $^2T_2 \rightarrow ^2E$ which occurs below $10000 cm^{-1}$. However, for pseudo-tetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes three peaks at 8500 ($\epsilon=48$), 13600 ($\epsilon=52$) and $21000 cm^{-1}$ have been reported²¹. Therefore, energy peaks observed in the present Cu^{II} complexes may be assigned in conformity with the earlier observations²² to a pseudo-tetrahedral configuration.

The electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes show three bands at $25550-23300$ ($\epsilon=5.2-5.5$), $15700-13960$ ($\epsilon=2.00-2.6$) and $8600-8400$ ($\epsilon=1.0-1.1$) cm^{-1} . These are assigned to $\nu_3[{}^3T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}]$, $\nu_2[{}^3T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}]$ and $\nu_1[{}^3T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}]$ transitions respectively, expected for octahedral Ni^{II} complexes. Out of these, the low energy band (ν_1) has been equated to $10 Dq$. The spectral parameters ν_2/ν_1 , Dq/B , B and β values have been found to be 1.70 , 1.1 , $872.5 cm^{-1}$ and 0.83 respectively. The lowering in the value of B from the free-ion value for Ni^{II} ($1040 cm^{-1}$) suggests 16.00% covalent nature of bonding. These values are close to those required for octahedral geometry²⁴.

The spectra of the Co^{II} complexes show two bands at $20490-20510$ ($\epsilon=1.9-2.4$) and $8740-8900$ ($\epsilon=1.3-2.0$) cm^{-1} , which are assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$,

respectively, of octahedral Co^{II} complex. The ν_2 band, since it involves a two-electron transition, was not observed. Its position was calculated using Koning equation²⁴. The spectral parameters ν_2/ν_1 , Dq/B , B and β values have been found in the range 2.00, 1.1, 826.08 cm^{-1} and 0.81 respectively, which agree with the literature value for octahedral Co^{II} complexes²³.

The Cr^{III} complexes exhibit bands at 17 100–17 140 ($\epsilon=16.8-17.0$), 21 190–21 200 ($\epsilon=16.9-17.1$) and 35 500–35 525 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon=21.0-21.4$) respectively, which may be assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{2g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_3) respectively. The spectral parameters ν_2/ν_1 , Dq/B , B and β values have been found to be 1.23, 1.18, 757.14 cm^{-1} and 0.73 respectively. These values are in good agreement with the reported values for octahedral Cr^{III} complexes²⁵.

Epr spectra : Epr spectra for the Cu^{II} complexes were recorded in DMF solution. For complexes with PADE show g_{II} and g_{I} values in the range 2.21–2.23 and 2.02–2.04 respectively, indicating the overall symmetry to be tetragonal around the Cu^{II} ion. No bands corresponding to $M_s = \pm 2$ transitions are observed in the spectrum ruling out any Cu–Cu interaction. g_{II} value less than 2.3 is indicative of metal-ligand bonding in these complexes as covalent²⁶. For the observed g value it is evident that the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The value 0.66–0.72 which is residence time of unpaired electron on Cu^{II} ion, indicates the covalent nature of Cu^{II} -ligand bonds. In the remaining complexes with MAQV and PAQV, well-defined splitting was not observed.

Nmr spectra : The ligands MAQV and PAQV showed signals at δ 2.2 (s, CH_3) and 7.5 (m, ArH) which remained unchanged in the metal chelates. The OCH_3 protons observed at δ 3.8 remained unaffected in the complexes. The azomethine proton suffering deshielding appears at δ 8.3–7.8 in all the complexes, indicating coordination of azomethine nitrogen.

Biological activity : The algacidal effects of CrCl_3 , CuCl_2 , CoCl_2 , NiCl_2 , the ligands MAQV and PAQV and their complexes with metal chlorides were studied on growth of a green alga *Chlorella* species. It was observed that ligands and the

complexes are less toxic than their corresponding metal chlorides. The order of toxicity among tested metal chlorides were observed as $\text{Cr} > \text{Cu} > \text{Ni} > \text{Co}$. The less toxic nature of complexes with respect to their metal salts may be attributed to their larger size. The ligand MAQV was more toxic than the ligand PAQV.

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